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Fueling exploitative and exploratory innovation with paternalistic leadership – do intrinsic motivation and environmental dynamism moderate the relationship?

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ABSTRACT

Keywords:

Paternalism

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Intrinsic motivation

Environmental dynamism

The objectives of the study were to investigate 1) whether paternalistic leadership affects exploitative and exploratory innovation, and 2) whether intrinsic motivation and environmental dynamism moderate the direct effects of paternalistic leadership on exploitative and exploratory innovation. The study was conducted in Sri Lanka by taking a sample of respondents from the information technology sector. The results indicate a notable distinction between the factors driving exploitative and exploratory innovation. Both types of innovations are significantly affected by paternalistic leadership. However, it has a positive influence on exploitation while it has a negative influence on exploration. Intrinsic motivation significantly predicts only the exploratory innovation, while environmental dynamism significantly predicts only the exploitative innovation. This divergence can be explained by the inherent differences in the nature of these two types of innovation. Overall, this research advances theoretical understanding and provides practical guidance.

1. Introduction

In the contemporary era of technological advancements, businesses find themselves navigating a dynamic environment characterized by rapid changes and fierce competition. Innovation is found to enhance firms' competitive positioning, profitability, and long-term sustainability by fostering differentiation, customer value creation, and market leadership in any chosen market. Hence, fostering individual innovation is vital for businesses to translate novel thoughts into either original or enhanced processes or products/services successfully. Exploitative and exploratory innovation are two main ways of achieving this success (March, 1991). Exploitative innovation places emphasis on gradual improvements or modifications to already-existing products, services or processes to enhance efficiency, reliability, and market performance (Levinthal & March, 1993). It ensures the optimization of currently available resources and capabilities to sustain short-term operational efficiency (He & Wong, 2004; Jansen et al., 2009). On the contrary, exploratory innovation places emphasis on the pursuit of new opportunities, experimentation, and risk-taking to explore novel ideas disrupting existing markets, technologies, or business models often leading to paradigm shifts and organization-wide transformations (He & Wong, 2004; March, 1991). Still, numerous studies have highlighted the importance of organizations effectively navigating both exploitative and exploratory innovation concurrently (Oehmichen et al., 2017; Vendrell-Herrero et al., 2023; Zuraik & Kelly, 2018).

At the core of this innovation journey is the impact of leadership, which is critical in advancing innovation initiatives. The present study investigated paternalistic leadership's influence on two types of innovation in organizations, i.e., exploratory and exploitative. As one of the prominent leadership styles, paternalistic leadership is commonly practised in Asian, Middle Eastern, Latin American, and African organizations (Aycan, 2015). When all these territories are taken together, paternalistic leadership is practised across most of the countries of the world. The leadership literature also highlights that paternalistic leadership is a viable explanation for organizations in the West (Ansari et al., 2004; Aycan, 2006; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). It is about the fit between a leader's style and that of his or her followers instead of the fit between a leader's style and geographic location (Ansari et al., 2004). Hence, East and West alike are interested in paternalistic leadership. As stated by Aycan (2006, p.446), "paternalism can be construed at the individual (e.g., paternalistic leadership), organizational (e.g., paternalistic organizational culture and practices), and socio-cultural levels (e.g., paternalism as a cultural dimension)". For example, culture and the support received by employees are important considerations in Asian cultures (Jayawardane & Wickramasinghe, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c). Hence, studies in different cultural contexts are important. Our study

investigated paternalistic leadership's influence on exploitative and exploratory innovation in organizations at the individual level. The study provides valuable insights into how organizations can leverage paternalistic leadership to drive innovation.

However, the interplay between leadership styles and innovation activities is found to be influenced by various contextual factors (De Costa & Wickramasinghe, 2025; Nanayakkara et al., 2022; Visser & Scheepers, 2022). Two such factors are intrinsic motivation and environmental dynamism (Chiu et al., 2024; Jansen et al., 2009). The intrinsic motivation of employees, characterized by their inherent drive to engage in meaningful work, may interact with leadership to shape innovation outcomes (Deci & Ryan, 1985). In addition, the dynamic nature of the external environment can impact the efficacy of leadership in fostering innovation (Damanpour & Schneider, 2009). Hence, we aim to investigate the possible moderating impact that intrinsic motivation and environmental dynamism have on the proposed direct effects involving paternalistic leadership on the two types of innovation.

Therefore, in the present study, we questioned 1) whether paternalistic leadership impacts exploitative and exploratory innovation, and 2) do intrinsic motivation and environmental dynamism moderate the relationship. Therefore, the objectives of the study were to investigate 1) whether paternalistic leadership affects exploitative and exploratory innovation, and 2) whether intrinsic motivation and environmental dynamism moderate the direct effects between paternalistic leadership and exploitative and exploratory innovation. To find answers to our research questions and to accomplish the set objectives, we conducted an empirical study in Sri Lanka by taking a sample of respondents from the information technology (IT) sector. This business sector in Sri Lanka provides a dynamic business landscape where innovation is a critical ingredient to stay competitive and foster long-term success. As reviewed in the next section, although different outcomes of paternalistic leadership in Asian, Middle Eastern, Latin American, African, and Western societies are studied, its effect on innovation has not been much investigated. Further, leadership studies on South Asia are very limited in the literature, and innovation is rarely a subject in almost all empirical studies on South Asia. In addition, it is difficult to find studies conducted in the context of the IT sector incorporating intrinsic motivation and environmental dynamism. Comprehending how intrinsic motivation and environmental dynamism modify these direct effects can offer valuable insights. Hence, our study adds to the corpus of the literature by elucidating the way paternalistic leadership operates on innovation and intrinsic motivation and environmental dynamism shape this important relationship.

2. Review of literature

2.1 *Exploitative and exploratory innovation*

Innovation encompasses diverse forms and manifestations, including technological breakthroughs, organizational strategies, social movements, and creative expressions. Schumpeter (1934) conceptualized innovation as the introduction of new products, processes, or market methods, emphasizing its role in driving economic development through the process of creative destruction. Building upon Schumpeter's seminal work (1934), subsequent scholars have expanded the notion of innovation and classified it using diverse dimensions. One of such primary distinctions of innovation is exploitative and exploratory innovation (March, 1991).

Exploitative innovation is a fundamental strategy for firms looking to improve existing products, services, and/or processes. March (1991) describes exploitative innovation as incremental improvements aimed at refining established designs and enhancing operational efficiency. Hence, unlike exploratory innovation, exploitative innovation relies on the optimization of existing knowledge and routines (Benner & Tushman, 2002; Levinthal & March, 1993). Benner and Tushman (2002) and Danneels (2002) stated that exploitative innovation helps organizations capitalize on existing capabilities and bolster market positions. Exploitative innovation, as suggested by March (1991), ensures firms' short-term survival by enhancing operational efficiency and streamlining processes. By building upon established technological trajectories, exploitative innovations enable firms to adapt to evolving market conditions and sustain competitiveness. Overall, exploitative innovation serves as a pragmatic approach for firms to improve existing products and processes. Its focus on incremental changes and efficiency enhancements is critical for firms aiming to navigate competitive environments and maintain market relevance.

Exploratory innovation, conversely, signifies a pivotal strategy for firms aiming to explore new markets and technologies. March (1991) defines exploratory innovation as efforts directed toward creating novel designs, market segments, and distribution channels. According to Benner and Tushman (2002), Danneels (2002), and Jansen et al. (2009), exploratory innovation is instrumental in addressing emerging customer needs and expanding business horizons. A key aspect of exploratory innovation, as highlighted by Benner and Tushman (2002) and Levinthal and March (1993), involves departing from existing knowledge frameworks. This departure allows firms to experiment with new ideas, take risks, and explore uncharted territories. Andriopoulos and Lewis (2009) emphasized the experimental nature of exploratory innovation, which often involves radical changes and the pursuit of new technological trajectories. March (1991) emphasised the long-term benefits of exploratory innovation, stating that while exploratory innovation may not yield immediate returns, it enhances firms' competitiveness and future income potential. Thus, exploratory innovations are critical in shaping firms' survival, growth,

and resilience in dynamic markets. Overall, exploratory innovation catalyses organizational growth by facilitating the exploration of new markets and technologies. Its experimental nature and focus on long-term benefits make it a strategic imperative for firms seeking to stay ahead in competitive landscapes.

2.2 Paternalistic leadership

Although paternalism is mainly attached to the family unit, Aycan et al. (2000, p.198) state that “paternalistic relationships go beyond family boundaries to reach the workplaces”. Paternalistic leadership is identified as a hierarchical relation between “a superior and subordinate in the organization context” (Aycan, 2006, p.446). Paternalistic leadership holds values of collectivistic and high-power distance societies (Bedi, 2020; Cheng et al., 2004; Huang & Lin, 2021; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008), including Sri Lanka (Gunasekara et al., 2022). There are unique characteristics attached to this leadership in the organizational context, as reviewed below.

First, a paternalistic leader “behaves in a fatherly manner towards his/her subordinates” as a part of the extended family (Aycan, 2006, p.448). The provision of individualized protection, guidance, nurturance, care, and many other forms of benefits to subordinates create a voluntary dependency relationship on the paternalistic leader, which spans both work and non-work domains (Aycan, 2006). Although a few previous studies highlight the negative effects of such efforts of paternalistic leaders on subordinates (Shaw & Liao, 2021), most research highlights positive effects on subordinates (Walker & Mercado, 2016).

Second, paternalistic leaders are role models who govern by moral principles and lead by virtue. In this regard, Aycan (2006, p.451), states that “the paternalistic leader assumes that he/she has superiority over his/her subordinate with respect to key competencies (knowledge, skills, and experience) as well as moral standards”. In succinct, paternalistic leaders display “strong discipline and authority together with fatherly compassion and moral integrity” (Cheng et al., 2004, p.102). In return, their expectation is loyalty and deference from subordinates (Aycan, 2006). Some previous studies suggest that subordinates should provide unquestioning obedience and compliance to their superiors (Cheng et al., 2004).

Third, paternalistic leadership thrives in a hierarchical organization system where inequality of power subsists between the leader and subordinates. Hence, it is understood as authoritative and manipulative, especially in individualistic societies (Osland, et al., 1999). For example, Osland, et al. (1999) state that paternalistic leaders can create “an organizational culture in which low performers are protected and tolerated”. In the Sri Lankan context, Jayasena et al. (2005), Wickramasinghe (2025), and Wickramasinghe and Madhusanka (2024) showed that organizational culture is an important determinant in employee behaviors. Fourth, Padavic and Earnest (1994) and Reed (1996) showed that paternalism not only occurs in high power distance cultures but also in lower power distance cultures in the context of manager and employee. Shaw and Liao (2021) state that ratings of paternalistic leader characteristics by subordinates could vary across Asian countries, but ratings of Asian countries are inevitably higher than those of Western countries. Still, as reviewed in the next section, paternalistic leadership is found to yield positive ramifications in societies in which paternalism is a desired characteristic (Aycan et al., 2000).

2.3 Paternalistic leadership and organization outcomes

Previous research showed many beneficial organisational outcomes when paternalistic ideology is applied, such as increased commitment, loyalty, productivity, and flexibility (Padavic & Earnest, 1994; Warren, 1999). According to Aycan (2006), the loyalty of subordinates is more valued than their job performance and the competencies they possess in developing countries. Further, subordinates “give their best to the job not to lose face for their beloved superiors”, and this is the “only possible way subordinates derive their sense of identity as members of “one big family”, which could lead to creating better working teams (Warren, 1999, p.53). Further, previous research showed that when paternalistic ideology is applied, cost reductions (Padavic & Earnest, 1994) and employee turnover reductions (Kim, 1994) generate a positive effect on organisational functioning. Aycan (2006, p.455) states that paternalism saves costs for the organization since paternalistic leaders allocate resources on “an individual basis, rather than for the entire workforce”, whereas Kim (1994, p.263) found that “managers in Korean organizations favoured in-kind benefits because this enables them to exercise control over employees”. In a recent study, Gardner and Wickramasinghe (2023) found that the fatherly compassion of paternalistic leaders promotes subordinates’ prosocial motivation to help others in their job roles, and this direct effect is moderated by self-transcendent values of the subordinates, where the moderation effect is stronger for low self-transcendent subordinates. Even in individualistic societies like the USA or broad in the North American context, paternalistic leadership characteristic of authoritarianism is found to produce subordinates’ satisfaction in task-oriented groups and increase subordinates’ organizational commitment (Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). Such findings support the argument of Ansari et al. (2004) that the concern is not the fit between the leadership and geographic location.

However, some research showed the negative effects of paternalistic leadership in the work context, such as loyalty expectations associated with superiors bullying subordinates, favouritism to selected subordinates and discrimination to selected subordinates (Aycan, 2015). Some other research showed that paternalism leads to creating angry emotions in subordinates and may develop fear towards superiors when subordinates' dependence is high on their superiors for job content, resources

to perform job content, and benefits for them thereafter (Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). Further, it is stated that paternalistic leaders' emphasis on hierarchy, obedience, and authority may hinder open communication, dissent, and constructive feedback (Chen et al., 2014). Moreover, paternalistic leadership may perpetuate dependence and passivity among employees, discouraging initiative, autonomy, and entrepreneurial behaviour (Cheng et al., 2004). Open communication, dissent, constructive feedback, initiative, autonomy, and entrepreneurial behaviour from subordinates are essential for driving innovation and adaptation in dynamic and competitive environments (Chen et al., 2014; Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe, 2017). While paternalistic leadership thrives in contexts characterized by high power distance and collectivism, its effectiveness in promoting innovative behaviour warrants further exploration (Saeed et al., 2019; Li et al., 2021). Hence, investigations are needed on the effectiveness of paternalistic leadership in promoting innovation.

2.3.1 Paternalistic leadership and innovation

A few previous studies have examined paternalistic leadership's influence on innovation. Wang and Cheng (2010) and Tian and Sanchez (2017) showed that paternalistic leadership style positively affect innovation. For example, Tian and Sanchez (2017) showed that authoritarian characteristics and the caring nature of paternalistic leadership promote subordinates' breakthrough behaviours across cultures. According to Tian and Sanchez (2017, p.1), paternalistic leaders' "demanding and yet selfless stance turns these leaders into prototypes of the subordinates' aspirational social identity". Further, the caring nature of paternalistic leadership promotes employees' innovative behaviour. However, a few studies, such as Li et al. (2021), Lu et al. (2022), Shaw and Liao (2021), and Yao and Hao (2023) showed a negative influence of paternalistic leadership on subordinates. For example, Shaw and Liao (2021) showed that the caring nature of paternalistic leadership negatively influences subordinates. In the Sri Lankan context, the findings of Swaris and Wickramasinghe (2024) also suggest that leadership style could affect new technology adoptions. In contrast, Yao and Hao (2023) and Lu et al. (2022) showed that both the caring nature and moral characteristics of paternalistic leadership have positive effects on employees' innovation behaviour and new venture performance, whereas its authoritarian characteristics have negative effects on the same. Further, Li et al. (2021) showed that the authoritarian character of paternalistic leadership thwarts subordinates' proactivity, which would diminish their motivation to bring forth new ideas". These conflicting conclusions of prior research addressing paternalistic leadership's effect on innovation warrant further exploration.

Further, most of the studies available in the literature investigated innovation in general. Against this backdrop, in the present study, we make a distinction between exploitative and exploratory innovation. In the realm of exploitative innovation, Wang et al. (2013) argue that paternalistic leaders' emphasis on stability, conformity, seeking to optimize existing processes, and adherence to established norms and procedures may inadvertently stifle creativity, risk-taking, and the pursuit of radical breakthroughs, potentially limiting the organization's capacity for exploitative innovation (also refer to Cheng et al., 2004). However, in the realm of exploratory innovation, paternalistic leaders may foster a supportive and nurturing environment conducive to exploratory innovation by providing guidance, support, and encouragement to employees to explore new horizons and take calculated risks (Chen et al., 2014). However, some previous research that investigated the effect of paternalistic leadership on exploitative and exploratory innovation does not agree with the above findings. For example, Hou et al. (2019, p.500) found that "benevolent and authoritarian leadership is positively related to exploratory innovation, while moral leadership has no significant impact on exploratory innovation". Their results also revealed that "all elements of paternalistic leadership are, in general, positively correlated with exploitative innovation" (Hou et al., 2019, p.500). These mixed findings warrant more research in this important area. Building on the majority of research reviewed above, it is proposed:

H₁: *Paternalistic leadership negatively affects exploitative innovation.*

H₂: *Paternalistic leadership positively affects exploratory innovation.*

2.4 Intrinsic motivation

Intrinsic motivation is a key driver of engagement in innovation. Previous studies have highlighted its positive association with employee innovation, emphasizing its role in fostering proactive behaviours and investment in exploring innovative solutions (Deci & Ryan, 1985; Amabile, 1983). For example, individuals with high levels of intrinsic motivation are inclined towards innovative behaviours and exhibit persistence in the face of challenges (Amabile, 1983). Further, highly intrinsically motivated employees in service innovation initiatives tend to be deeply engaged, viewing work as enjoyable rather than burdensome (Kim & Lee, 2013). Furthermore, intrinsic motivation is found to be correlated with creativity, suggesting that individuals with elevated levels demonstrate greater innovativeness and initiative (Dysvik & Kuvaas, 2013). In addition, intrinsic motivation plays a pivotal role in employee innovation, fostering perseverance, unconventional problem-solving approaches, and creativity (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Tuan & Lu, 2013). Although previous research investigated the effect of intrinsic motivation on exploitative and exploratory inventions, building on the above reviewed literature, it is proposed:

H₃: *Intrinsic motivation positively affects exploitative innovation.*

H₄: *Intrinsic motivation positively affects exploratory innovation.*

However, the literature suggests that connections between paternalistic leadership and exploitative and exploratory innovations are multifaceted and could be contingent upon individual contextual factors like intrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation that is rooted in individuals' internal drive to be involved in actions for their inherent pleasure and satisfaction (Deci & Ryan, 1985) could influence responses to paternalistic leadership behaviours to drive exploitative innovation. That is, while paternalistic leaders may provide a supportive and nurturing environment, intrinsic motivation may serve as an additional source of drive and satisfaction, potentially impacting employees' engagement in exploitative innovation (Amabile, 1983; Chen et al., 2014; Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe, 2017). Li et al. (2024) found that the association between employees' involvement in exploratory innovation and paternalistic leadership was strengthened by intrinsic motivation, with advanced levels of intrinsic motivation leading to greater innovation outcomes. Lee et al. (2018), however, suggested that while paternalistic leadership may influence exploitative innovation within organizations, intrinsic motivation may not significantly moderate this relationship. Hence, the precise role of intrinsic motivation remains nuanced, with divergent findings across different studies. Hence, it is proposed for the present study:

H₅: *Intrinsic motivation moderates the effect of paternalistic leadership on exploitative innovation.*

H₆: *Intrinsic motivation moderates the effect of paternalistic leadership on exploratory innovation.*

2.5 Environmental dynamism

The term environmental dynamism denotes the frequency and extent of change and uncertainty in the external environment. The literature suggests the profound influence environmental dynamism has on organizational adaptability and innovation (Auh & Menguc, 2005). For example, Auh and Menguc (2005) emphasize that as the dynamism of the environment increases, organizations are compelled to strike a balance between exploitative and exploratory innovation. Accordingly, organizations facing high environmental dynamism are compelled to pursue exploratory innovation to capitalize on emerging opportunities while maintaining exploitative innovation to ensure survival (Auh and Menguc, 2005). As per Waldman et al. (2001), high levels of environmental dynamism heighten uncertainty and complexity, which in turn encourages the organization's propensity for innovation. It is proposed:

H₇: *Environmental dynamism positively affects exploitative innovation.*

H₈: *Environmental dynamism positively affects exploratory innovation.*

Environmental dynamism can also operate as another contextual factor that could influence the connection between paternalistic leadership and exploitative and exploratory inventions. Environmental dynamism could significantly influence the effectiveness of leadership styles in fostering innovation (Hou et al., 2019; Waldman et al., 2001). In stable environments, paternalistic leaders provide a sense of security and stability, thereby promoting trust and commitment among subordinates, which are crucial for innovation initiatives. However, under conditions of high environmental dynamism, paternalistic leadership may impede innovation by stifling creativity and risk-taking (Pérez-Luño et al., 2014). Further, paternalistic leaders' emphasis on stability, harmony, and hierarchical control may facilitate the implementation of incremental improvements and optimization of existing processes in stable environments. However, in dynamic environments characterized by rapid changes and uncertainty, paternalistic leadership may face challenges in promoting exploitative innovation. The hierarchical nature of paternalistic leadership may adversely influence an organizations agility and responsiveness to opportunities and threats of the environment (Cheng et al., 2004). Hence, it is proposed:

H₉: Environmental dynamism moderates the effect of paternalistic leadership on exploitative innovation

H₁₀: Environmental dynamism moderates the effect of paternalistic leadership on exploratory innovation

3. Methodology

3.1 Measures

Five constructs were used in the study. To ensure consistency in response format, each construct was evaluated on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Five measurement scales were used in the study, namely, paternalistic leadership (Aycan et al., 2000), exploratory innovation (Mom et al., 2007), exploitative innovation (Mom et al., 2007), environmental dynamism (Jansen et al., 2009), and intrinsic motivation (Tierney et al., 1999).

3.2 Sample

Hundred and fifty-seven individuals who engaged directly in innovation activities were selected with convenience sampling from 15 IT firms in Sri Lanka. Four per cent of the respondents were in the age range 18 - 24 years, 76% were in the age range 25 - 34 years, and 20% were 35 years of age or older. Sixty-one per cent identified them as males and 39% identified them as females. Regarding education level, 98% had bachelor's degrees while the rest reported having postgraduate qualifications. This suggests the significance of educational qualifications within the IT sector. Regarding respondents' perception of the market presence of their respective firms, 36% identified their firms as established entities, 23% identified their firms as pioneering entities, 31% identified their firms as emerging entities, and 10% identified their firms as niche players.

Regarding the firm size by the number of employees, 14% of the respondents identified their respective firms as small-sized entities with up to 49 employees, 53% identified as medium-sized entities ranging from 50 to 249 employees, and 33% identified as large-sized entities with 250 or more employees.

3.3 Data collection method

A survey-based approach was utilized for data collection. The questionnaire was distributed electronically to participants, utilizing secure online survey platforms to facilitate efficient data collection and management. Respondents had the option to respond anonymously. Clear instructions were provided regarding the completion of the questionnaire. Follow-up reminders were sent at regular intervals to maximize response rates and ensure adequate representation within the sample.

3.4 Methods of data analysis

First, data were tested for validity and reliability. For all constructs, values of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure were statistically significant ($p < .001$). Second, principal component factor analysis was used. The measures of factor analysis are shown in Table 1. Regression analysis with Hayes' process macro was performed to test the relationships.

Table 1

Fit measures of the factor analysis

Construct	No. of factors extracted	Eigenvalue	Variance explained	Cronbach's alpha
Paternalistic leadership	1	3.5	69.99	.889
Exploratory innovation	1	3.848	76.961	.920
Exploitative innovation	1	3.170	63.392	.851
Intrinsic motivation	1	3.327	66.530	.872
Environment dynamism	1	2.843	56.071	.738

4. Findings

First, regression analysis with Hayes' process macro was performed to test the relationships involving exploitative innovation. According to the R-squared value, 37.74% of the variability is predicted by the model, and the model as a whole is significant ($p < .001$, $F = 18.309$). Hypotheses 1, 3, 5, 7, and 9 are for the proposed relationships involving paternalistic leadership on exploitative innovation. Table 2 shows the model summary for this regression analysis. The unstandardized regression weight for paternalistic leadership is $-.173$ ($p < .01$), indicating a negative effect between paternalistic leadership and exploitative innovation. Hence, H1 is supported. The impact of intrinsic motivation on exploitative innovation is $.133$ ($p > .05$). Hence, H3 is not supported. The moderator effect of intrinsic motivation is $-.049$ ($p > .05$), which does not support H5. The impact of environmental dynamism on exploitative innovation is $.515$ ($p < .001$), supporting H7. The moderator effect of environmental dynamism is $-.078$ ($p > .05$), indicating that the moderating effect is not significant. Hence, H9 is not supported.

Table 2

Paternalistic leadership on exploitative innovation, moderated by intrinsic motivation and environmental dynamism

Variable	Regression weight	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Paternalistic leadership	-.173	.055	-3.130	.0021	-.282	-.063
Intrinsic motivation	.133	.102	1.295	.1971	-.069	.336
Int_1	-.049	.095	-.512	.6092	-.238	.140
Environmental dynamism	.515	.084	6.105	.0000	.348	.682
Int_2	-.078	.079	-.980	.3284	-.235	.079

Note: Int_1 = Interaction effect of intrinsic motivation; Int_2 = Interaction effect of environmental dynamism

Second, regression analysis with Hayes' process macro was performed to test the relationships involving exploratory innovation. According to the R-squared value, 20.36% of the variability is predicted by the model, and the model as a whole is significant ($p < .001$, $F = 7.720$). Hypotheses 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 are for the proposed relationships involving paternalistic leadership on exploitative innovation. Table 3 shows the model summary for this regression analysis. The unstandardized regression weight for paternalistic leadership is $.434$ ($p < .001$), supporting H2. The impact of intrinsic motivation on exploratory innovation is $.362$ ($p < .05$). Hence, H4 is supported. The moderator effect of intrinsic motivation is $-.1059$ ($p > .05$), which does not support H6. The impact of environmental dynamism on exploratory innovation is $-.140$ ($p > .05$), which does not support H8. The moderator effect of environmental dynamism is $.128$ ($p > .05$), indicating that the moderating effect is not significant. Hence, H10 is not supported. The summary of the hypothesis testing is given in Table 4.

Table 3**Paternalistic leadership on exploratory innovation, moderated by intrinsic motivation and environmental dynamism**

Variable	Regression weight	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Paternalistic leadership	.434	.090	4.794	.0000	.255	.614
Intrinsic motivation	.362	.168	2.150	.0332	.029	.695
Int_1	-.105	.157	-.672	.5024	-.417	.205
Environmental dynamism	-.140	.138	-1.012	.3129	-.414	.133
Int_2	.128	.130	.985	.3261	-.129	.386

Note: Int_1 = Interaction effect of intrinsic motivation; Int_2 = Interaction effect of environmental dynamism

Table 4**Summary of hypotheses testing**

Hypothesis	Result
H1 Paternalistic leadership negatively affects exploitative innovation	Supported
H2 Paternalistic leadership positively affects exploratory innovation	Supported
H3 Intrinsic motivation positively affects exploitative innovation	Not supported
H4 Intrinsic motivation positively affects exploratory innovation	Supported
H5 Intrinsic motivation moderates the effect of paternalistic leadership on exploitative innovation	Not supported
H6 Intrinsic motivation moderates the effect of paternalistic leadership on exploratory innovation	Not supported
H7 Environmental dynamism positively affects exploitative innovation	Supported
H8 Environmental dynamism positively affects exploratory innovation	Not supported
H9 Environmental dynamism moderates the effect of paternalistic leadership on exploitative innovation	Not supported
H10 Environmental dynamism moderates the effect of paternalistic leadership on exploratory innovation	Not supported

5. Discussion of findings, conclusion and implications*5.1. Discussion of findings*

The study aimed to investigate 1) whether paternalistic leadership affects exploitative and exploratory innovation, and 2) whether intrinsic motivation and environmental dynamism moderate the direct effects between paternalistic leadership and exploitative and exploratory innovation. The results showed key distinctions between the factors influencing the two types of innovation. First, paternalistic leadership significantly positively impact exploratory innovation. However, it significantly negatively impacts exploitative innovation. This suggests that paternalistic leadership, which combines elements of authority and benevolence, fosters a creative and experimental environment that supports the generation of new ideas. Those who adopt this leadership style are likely to drive exploration within their teams, which is essential for fostering innovation in new areas. However, the negative impact of paternalistic leadership on exploitative innovation indicates that it may not be as effective in driving efficiency-oriented improvements. This could be due to the fact that paternalistic leadership emphasizes individualized attention and care, which may divert focus from refining existing processes and optimizing efficiency.

Second, intrinsic motivation played a significant role in fostering exploratory innovation. However, intrinsic motivation did not significantly affect exploitative innovation. Intrinsic motivation encourages individuals to engage in creative activities and exploration. This aligns with the principles of self-determination, which suggests that intrinsic motivation is vital for fostering curiosity, autonomy, and the desire to pursue new challenges. On the other hand, intrinsic motivation did not significantly affect exploitative innovation, which tends to focus on the improvement of existing processes and routines. Exploitative innovation often requires a more structured environment, which may depend more on external factors, such as organizational constraints and market demands, rather than intrinsic motivation alone.

Third, environmental dynamism was found to significantly influence exploitative innovation but not exploratory innovation. Environmental dynamism that defies external changes and uncertainty in the business environment drives organizations to adapt their existing processes in response to changing conditions. This is particularly important for exploitative innovation, which focuses on improving and optimizing current practices to maintain competitive advantage. However, environmental dynamism did not significantly affect exploratory innovation, which is more internally driven and less dependent on external environmental factors. This suggests that while external changes influence the refinement of existing processes, they have less influence on the exploration of new ideas, which is often more driven by internal motivations and leadership.

Fourth, the interaction effects of intrinsic motivation and environmental dynamism were not significant. Despite the hypotheses that both intrinsic motivation and environmental dynamism would moderate the proposed relationships, it was found that neither variable substantially altered the direct effects. This suggests that the effects of paternalistic leadership on innovation are more direct than initially anticipated, with paternalistic leadership independently influencing both types of innovation without significant interaction from intrinsic motivation and environmental dynamism. It is possible that the moderating effects of these variables are context-dependent and may vary in different organizational settings or under different conditions.

5.2 Conclusion

The results indicate a notable distinction between the factors driving exploitative and exploratory innovation. Both types of innovations are significantly affected by paternalistic leadership. However, it has a positive influence on exploitation while it has a negative influence on exploration. Paternalistic leadership with encouragement for exploration and risk-taking within their teams manage to foster exploratory innovation. However, paternalistic leadership's emphasis on individualized attention and care may hinder focus from driving efficiency-oriented improvements. The analysis reveals that intrinsic motivation significantly predicts only exploratory innovation. Environmental dynamism significantly predicts only exploitative innovation. This divergence can be explained by the inherent differences in the nature of these two types of innovation. Exploitative innovation is about refining prevailing processes, increasing efficiency, and leveraging known capabilities. As these activities often require adaptation to changes in the external environment, principles of contingency theory support this significant role of environmental dynamism in driving exploitative innovation. In contrast, exploratory innovation centres on experimentation, creativity, and the pursuit of new ideas. Since these behaviours are largely self-driven, they align with the principles of self-determination, which highlights how intrinsic motivation fosters autonomy, curiosity, and a desire for learning - all of which are essential for exploration. Therefore, while exploratory innovation is primarily driven by internal motivational forces, exploitative innovation is shaped by external environmental pressures, underscoring the need for firms to foster intrinsic motivation for exploratory efforts while remaining agile and responsive to environmental changes to drive exploitative innovation.

Overall, this research advances theoretical understanding and provides practical guidance. It highlights the importance of aligning leadership strategies with the nature of the innovation goal, whether it is exploration or exploitation. By fostering a leadership environment that supports intrinsic motivation and responds to environmental changes, firms can achieve a more effective balance between creative exploration and operational efficiency. Similarly, intrinsic motivation emerges as a vital driver for exploration, whereas environmental dynamism plays a crucial role in exploitation. These insights emphasize the need for organizations to recognize and manage the distinctive demands of the two innovation types rather than applying a one-size-fits-all approach.

5.3 Theoretical implications

This study provided much-needed findings on the complex dynamics between paternalistic leadership, intrinsic motivation, environmental dynamism, and their collective impact on exploratory and exploitative innovation in Sri Lanka's IT industry. The findings demonstrate that leadership styles, internal motivation, and external environmental factors play distinct roles in shaping these two forms of innovation. This study offers several significant theoretical implications for the fields of leadership, motivation, and innovation management.

First, it advances the understanding of how paternalistic leadership influences dual innovation pathways – exploitative and exploratory innovation. The findings challenge the conventional notion that a single leadership style can uniformly drive both types of innovation. Instead, the study reveals that paternalistic leadership fosters exploratory innovation while hindering exploitative innovation, thereby supporting the duality perspective of ambidextrous innovation. Hence, the findings support the arguments of Andriopoulos and Lewis (2009), He and Wong (2004), and Oehmichen et al. (2017). This insight contributes to leadership theory emphasizing the differential effects of paternalistic leadership on distinct innovation types.

Second, the study reinforces the relevance of self-determination in explaining intrinsic motivation's role in driving exploratory innovation. It was found that intrinsic motivation plays a pivotal role in stimulating exploration, aligning with principles of self-determination with emphasis on autonomy, curiosity, and self-initiative as precursors to creativity and learning, as suggested by Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe (2017). By linking self-determination to exploratory innovation, this study deepens the theoretical understanding of how intrinsic motivation drives individual and organizational-level exploration.

Third, the role of contingency theory is underscored by incorporating environmental dynamism's effect on exploitative innovation. It was revealed that firms in dynamic environments engage in exploitative innovation, as the need for adaptability and responsiveness to environmental changes increases. This extends the theoretical understanding of environmental dynamism as a context-dependent variable, which shapes exploitative innovation pursued by organizations. The findings emphasize the situational nature of innovation, showing that environmental pressures compel firms to prioritize exploitation over exploration in certain conditions.

Finally, the study bridges the gap between leadership theory and innovation theory by examining how leadership styles interact with motivational and environmental factors. While prior studies have explored leadership and motivation separately, this study integrates them, providing a more holistic theoretical framework for understanding innovation. The identification of moderation effects in the present study offers a nuanced view of how different contextual variables jointly shape innovation outcomes. This integrated approach contributes to theoretical advancements in leadership and innovation

literature by providing an interactionist perspective on innovation antecedents. These theoretical insights offer a more comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms through which leadership, motivation, and environmental context shape organizational innovation. Future studies can build on these theoretical contributions to explore other leadership styles or contextual factors, thereby enriching the conceptual framework for ambidextrous innovation.

5.4 Implications for practice

The study's key contribution lies in its distinction between the determinants of innovation, i.e., exploratory and exploitative. While paternalistic leadership fosters exploratory innovation, it presents challenges for exploitative innovation. The findings offer several critical practical implications for organizations, especially those operating in dynamic and innovation-driven industries. First, paternalistic leadership's dual role in fostering exploratory innovation while inhibiting exploitative innovation suggests the necessity for a more nuanced approach to leadership. Managers should recognize that different styles of leadership may be required depending on the type of innovation the organization aims to achieve. For exploratory innovation, leaders should foster a climate that encourages creativity, autonomy, and experimentation, which aligns with the characteristics of exploratory innovation. On the contrary, for exploitative innovation, leaders may need to emphasize efficiency, control, and adherence to processes. Initiative for leadership development should be designed to facilitate managers with the skills to shift to a paternalistic style depending on the context and organizational priorities. This approach will enable firms to enjoy the benefits of both types of innovation, thus promoting ambidexterity - pursuing both simultaneously.

Second, the study showed the role of intrinsic motivation in driving exploratory innovation. Since the study found that intrinsic motivation significantly affects exploratory innovation, organizations should adopt strategies to nurture and sustain employees' internal drive for exploration. This can be achieved by offering employees greater autonomy, promoting creative freedom, and encouraging self-initiated projects. When employees have the opportunity to engage in challenging, meaningful tasks, their intrinsic motivation is likely to increase, thereby boosting exploratory innovation. Organizations should incorporate this insight into human resource practices, such as employee recognition programs and learning and development initiatives. For instance, firms could design "innovation sprints" or "creative challenge sessions" where employees are encouraged to work on novel ideas outside their routine tasks. By creating an organizational culture that promotes curiosity and intrinsic motivation, firms can enhance their capacity for exploratory innovation, which is essential for long-term growth and competitiveness.

Third, the study's findings on the role of environmental dynamism provide further practical guidance. Environmental dynamism was shown to significantly impact exploitative innovation, suggesting that firms operating in rapidly changing environments are more likely to focus on refining existing processes and leveraging current capabilities. In such dynamic contexts, organizations should develop agile systems and adaptive business models to respond effectively to environmental changes. This can be achieved through the implementation of flexible workflows, decision-making based on real-time data, and analysis for anticipative shifts in market demand. Managers should remain vigilant to industry changes, and firms should promote continuous learning initiatives to help employees adapt to new market conditions. Additionally, organizations may consider developing agile project teams that can shift their focus from exploratory to exploitative innovation as needed, ensuring that the firm remains resilient and responsive in times of uncertainty.

Fourth, an essential practical repercussion of this study is the need for organizations to maintain a balance between two types of innovations - exploratory and exploitative. Firms should adopt an ambidextrous approach, creating separate units or teams dedicated to exploration and exploitation. For instance, while R&D departments can be tasked with exploring new ideas and opportunities, operational teams may be responsible for optimizing existing processes and driving efficiency. Companies could also implement cross-functional teams that allow employees to alternate between exploratory and exploitative roles, thereby fostering knowledge sharing and cross-pollination of ideas. Performance measurement systems should also reflect this dual focus, with clear key performance indicators for both exploration and exploitation. Managers should ensure that neither dimension is neglected, as overemphasizing one form of innovation at the expense of the other can hinder the firm's long-term competitiveness.

Fifth, the study also offers valuable insights for policymakers and industry regulators. Since environmental dynamism promotes exploitative innovation, policymakers should consider creating an enabling environment that fosters industry dynamism. By promoting technological change, regulatory flexibility, and access to funding, policymakers can encourage firms to innovate continuously. For instance, governments can introduce grant schemes and tax incentives to support firms engaged in process optimization and efficiency improvement. Regulatory frameworks should also be flexible enough to accommodate new business models and emerging technologies. In turn, these measures would support firms in maintaining their competitiveness in fast-evolving markets, such as the IT industry.

6. Limitations and future research

One of the limitations is the geographical and industry-specific focus on the Sri Lankan IT sector. While the findings offer valuable insights for firms in this context, the generalizability of the results to other industries or countries is important.

Comparative studies across multiple countries would provide a more comprehensive view of the role of paternalistic leadership, especially in cross-cultural management. A further limitation is the exclusive reliance on self-reported data, although statistical methods were applied to detect and control any issues in self-reported data. Therefore, collecting data from multiple sources, such as supervisor evaluations, team-based assessments, or objective performance metrics could be beneficial in the future.

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